

DiSSCo related output

This template collects the required metadata to reference the official Deliverables and Milestones of DiSSCo-related projects. More information on the mandatory and conditionally mandatory fields can be found in the supporting document 'Metadata for DiSSCo Knowledge base' that is shared among work package leads, and in Teamwork > Files. A short explanatory text is given for all metadata fields, thus allowing easy entry of the required information. If there are any questions, please contact us at info@dissco.eu.

Title

Design of the DiSSCo policy framework tool: DiSSCo Prepare WP 7 – Milestone 7.5

Author(s)

Lisa French, Matt Woodburn, Jonathan Blettery, Ana Casino, Quentin Groom, Marko Hyvarinen, Tina Loo, Carole Paleco, Julia Pim Reis, Serge Scory, Patrick Semal, Laura Tilley and Vincent Smith

Identifier of the author(s)

LF: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7279-8582>
MW: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6496-1423>
JB: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2139-2926>
AC: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9869-6573>
QG: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0596-5376>
MH: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8736-0946>
TL: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8250-1786>
CP: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2981-5436>
JPR: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4383-0357>
SS: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2692-8651>
PS: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4048-7728>
LT: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2455-7992>
VS: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5297-7452>

Affiliation

LF, MW, VS: Natural History Museum, London
JB: National Museum of Natural History, Paris
AC, LT: Consortium of European taxonomic Facilities
QG: Meise Botanic Garden
MH: Finnish Museum of Natural History
TL: Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden
CP, SS, PS: Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
JPR: Museum für Naturkunde

Contributors

Publisher

Identifier of the publisher

Resource ID

Publication year

2021

Related identifiers

Is it the first time you submit this outcome?

Yes

Creation date

15/04/2021

Version

Citation

French, L., Woodburn, M., Blettery, J., Casino, A., Groom, Q., Hyvarinen, M., Loo, T., Paleco, C., Pim Reis, J., Scory, S., Semal, P., Tilley L. and Smith, V.S. 2021. Design of the DiSSCo policy framework tool. DiSSCo Prepare WP 7 – Milestone 7.5. pp1-20.

Abstract

To develop the organisational readiness of DiSSCo, we need to ensure the related policies of DiSSCo members align with the needs of DiSSCo services. Work in previous projects has shown that the complex governance structures and fragmented policy frameworks of DiSSCo members mean that direct imposition of a new set of DiSSCo service policies would be extremely difficult. Instead, we sought to develop an alternative approach, measuring institutional compliance with DiSSCo policy needs through the development of a new software tool. This tool must 1) support the self-assessment and development of member institutions existing policy frameworks against DiSSCo service needs; and 2) support the DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office (CSO), or its successor, in their efforts to demonstrate and incentivise policy alignment. The following document (DiSSCo Prepare Milestone 7.5) provides a blueprint for the technical features for such a tool based on a set of functional and non-functional requirements, expressed as acceptance criteria. These are drawn from a set of user stories, developed through a series of interviews and meetings with policy stakeholders. The criteria are accompanied by definitions, user roles and workflow descriptions that would enable the technical development of the tool, as outlined in the associated Deliverable 7.3, due for completion in July 2022. Throughout the development of this technical blueprint, we became aware of a set of closely related technical needs to support the self-assessment of member institutions digital maturity (DiSSCo Prepare Task 3.1). While these needs are described separately, their potential synergy should be taken into account when building a technical solution that addresses these policy requirements.

Content keywords

technical

Project reference

DiSSCo Prepare (GA-871043)

WP number

WP7

Project output

Milestone report

Deliverable/milestone number

7.5

Dissemination level

Public

Rights**License**

Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

Resource type

Text

Format

PDF

Funding Programme

H2020-INFRADEV-2019-2

Contact email
vince@vsmith.info

Design of the DiSSCo policy framework tool

DiSSCo Prepare WP 7 – Milestone 7.5

Lisa French, Matt Woodburn, Jonathan Blettery, Ana Casino,
Quentin Groom, Marko Hyvarinen, Tina Loo, Carole Paleco, Julia Pim
Reis, Serge Scory, Patrick Semal, Laura Tilley and Vincent Smith.

Abstract

To develop the organisational readiness of DiSSCo, we need to ensure the related policies of DiSSCo members align with the needs of DiSSCo services. Work in previous projects has shown that the complex governance structures and fragmented policy frameworks of DiSSCo members mean that direct imposition of a new set of DiSSCo service policies would be extremely difficult. Instead, we sought to develop an alternative approach, measuring institutional compliance with DiSSCo policy needs through the development of a new software tool. This tool must 1) support the self-assessment and development of member institutions existing policy frameworks against DiSSCo service needs; and 2) support the DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office (CSO), or its successor, in their efforts to demonstrate and incentivise policy alignment. The following document (DiSSCo Prepare Milestone 7.5) provides a blueprint for the technical features for such a tool based on a set of functional and non-functional requirements, expressed as acceptance criteria. These are drawn from a set of user stories, developed through a series of interviews and meetings with policy stakeholders. The criteria are accompanied by definitions, user roles and workflow descriptions that would enable the technical development of the tool, as outlined in the associated Deliverable 7.3, due for completion in July 2022. Throughout the development of this technical blueprint, we became aware of a set of closely related technical needs to support the self-assessment of member institutions digital maturity (DiSSCo Prepare Task 3.1). While these needs are described separately, their potential synergy should be taken into account when building a technical solution that addresses these policy requirements.

Key words

Policy, services, alignment, standards, DiSSCo, tool, design, specification, requirements, blueprint

H2020-INFRADEV-2019-2
Grant Agreement No 871043

Grant Agreement number: 871043 — DiSSCo Prepare — H2020-INFRADEV-2018-2020 / H2020-INFRADEV-2019-2

Contents

Contents	3
1 Introduction	4
2 Methodology	5
3 Overview of the Policy Tool	5
3.1 Concept Definitions	5
3.2 Statement of Purpose	6
3.3 Process Diagram	7
3.4 User Roles	7
3.5 User Stories	8
4 Requirements	10
4.1 DiSSCo Policy Portal	10
4.1.1 Description	10
4.1.2 Acceptance Criteria	11
4.2 Self Assessment Tool	12
4.2.1 Description	12
4.2.2 Acceptance Criteria	12
4.3 Institutional Summary	13
4.3.1 Description	13
4.3.2 Acceptance Criteria	13
4.4 DiSSCo CSO Dashboard	14
4.4.1 Description	14
4.4.2 Acceptance Criteria	14
5 Non Functional Requirements	15
6 Project Dependencies	18
6.1 SYNTHESYS+ NA2.1: Harmonisation of Policies and Best Standards	18
6.2 DiSSCo Prepare Task 5.1: Knowledgebase	18
6.3 DiSSCo Prepare Task 3.1: Digital maturity tool	18
7 General Issues and Challenges	19
8 Conclusion	20
9 Author Contributions	20

1 Introduction

For DiSSCo institutions to operate as a single unified service to its users, it is essential that there be a level of harmony in their policies that would allow smooth functioning of DiSSCo services within the Research Infrastructure. These policies include those related to physical access to specimens, and digital access to surrogates of these specimens, such as digital images and specimen metadata. Nevertheless, there will inevitably be variations in policies between institutions and countries or regions, and policies evolve in time and at different rates. Therefore, understanding the policy landscape of DiSSCo members is necessary for the functioning and management of DiSSCo Research Infrastructure, both centrally, and nationally, and at the level of each member.

Outputs from other DiSSCo-linked projects (namely ICEDIG and SYNTHESYS+) have demonstrated just how complex the existing operational policy landscape is for many DiSSCo-linked community members. For example, many institutions operate with considerable policy gaps, they are written in a multitude of languages, structured in a multiplicity of ways and sit under a variety of complex governance structures and national legislation, much of which is beyond the scope, and furthermore, the capacity of DiSSCo to influence. Despite this, investigative work suggests that many of the DiSSCo service policy needs are already covered in existing institutional policy handbooks, so rather than force a new set of DiSSCo service policies on to institutions, it was considered easier to align the outcomes of these existing policies, and incentivise change when necessary, to accommodate the emerging needs of DiSSCo services.

Within Task 7.3 we set about developing the requirements for this tool, building on the outcomes from prior work and developing synergies with ongoing DiSSCo activities. Central to the operation of the Policy Tool is some means to markup existing institutional and DiSSCo policies such that their contents and outcomes could be both human and machine readable. This requires a metadata schema, providing a common vocabulary that would allow the tool to compare the contents of existing policies, develop the necessary data visualisations aggregating policy positions of different institutions, and enable the tool to make inferences on policy positions. This policy metadata schema is in development as part of SYNTHESYS+ Task 2.1, and there has been close collaboration between participants of these two tasks throughout the development of this milestone.

Related to this metadata schema, is the need to create a place of deposit for institutional policies and/or their contents, marked-up through the metadata schema. The place of deposit needs to be accessible to the Policy Tool and is being addressed through development of the DiSSCo Prepare Knowledge base (DPP Task 5.1). As a consequence, there has been close collaboration to ensure associated requirements of the Policy Tool can be met within the Knowledge base.

Another point of synergy emerged through the development of the Policy Tool requirements, via analysis of related work in DPP Task 3.1. This task is developing a DiSSCo Digital Maturity Tool, enabling institutions to self-assess their digital competences against the needs of DiSSCo. While the content of such a tool are very different to those for assessing policy, the basic principle of performing self-assessment activities against a set of criteria, and the need to access an aggregated dataset showing these results by the DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office (CSO), is identical. To this end we have worked closely with Task 3.1 to ensure that the basic principles of both tools are

sufficiently aligned that, if circumstances allow, the needs coming from both can be accommodated in the same technical platform.

We recommend that the CSO explore the same alignment process with other tools and products developed under the umbrella of the DiSSCo-related projects landscape, as it could be the case for the Digitisation Dashboard developed under T2.2. in SYNTHESYS+.

2 Methodology

User stories for the Policy Tool were developed through consultation with the seven DiSSCo Prepare Task 7.3 partner institutions. Semi-structured user interviews were conducted with institutional policy owners (e.g., registrars, unit directors, curators), as well as with stakeholders from the SYNTHESYS+ Virtual Access Work Package. These user stories build on the work of the ICEDIG D7.1 Policy Analysis task.

The user stories were used to develop the functional requirements for the Policy Tool, which were written in the form of acceptance criteria. Each acceptance criteria is associated with a user story, and they set out the functionality required in order for the user story to be complete.

3 Overview of the Policy Tool

3.1 Concept Definitions

Term	Description
Distributed System of Scientific Collections Research Infrastructure (DiSSCo RI)	A pan-European Research Infrastructure mobilising, unifying and delivering bio and geo-diversity digital information to scientific communities.
DiSSCo service	DiSSCo will have a range of services across three categories: e-Sciences, physical and remote access, support and training.
DiSSCo member	An organisation that has signed the European Memorandum of Understanding to join DiSSCo. There are currently over 120 institutions across 21 European countries.
DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office (CSO)	The DiSSCo CSO is responsible for the implementation of the work programs of the DiSSCo preparatory and construction stages.
National Node	DiSSCo members are organised into National Nodes with a national coordinator.

European Loans and Visits System (ELViS)	A unified pan-European system for managing loans and visits access to any collection for any authorised user under a consistent access policy (for restrictions, responsibilities, reporting, etc.).
Policy	A documented policy within the scope of DiSSCo
DiSSCo Policy	A policy adopted by the DiSSCo RI
Institutional Policy	A policy adopted by a DiSSCo member institution
Policy owner	The person within an organisation responsible for a policy.
Policy Self-Assessment	The act of an institution comparing its policies against a common policy framework.
Metadata schema	A metadata schema outlines a common understanding of the elements, attributes and properties of the metadata. A DiSSCo policy metadata schema is under development as part of the SYNTHESYS+ Network Access (NA) 2.1 task.
Dashboard	A dashboard is a visual tool that summarises key information relating to performance and progress against certain aims and objectives. It often includes graphic visualisations of the data, and may include interactive features such as filters and drilldowns to the underlying data

3.2 Statement of Purpose

DiSSCo Prepare Task 7.3 will develop an online self-assessment which will allow a DiSSCo member to map their institutional policies against the policy requirements of DiSSCo services to ascertain policy existence, alignment and/or compliance. For the DiSSCo RI the Policy Tool will allow them to view the overall policy alignment across all DiSSCo members, For DiSSCo members, the tool will support their efforts to deliver institutional policy compliance and follow best practices and implement tested protocols and procedures.

The Policy Tool will:

- Support the upload or linkage of policies;
- Support deposition of a list of the policy requirements of the DiSSCo RI for the different DiSSCo services;
- Contain a classification of terms (metadata schema) for these policies and services;
- Supports evaluation of alignment between institutional policies and DiSSCo service policies, through an institutional self-assessment checklist that uses the metadata schema.

3.3 Process Diagram

3.4 User Roles

Term	Description
Institutional Policy Lead	A user who is responsible for at least one institutional policy within a DiSSCo member institution. This can include curators, collection managers and registrars.
DiSSCo CSO user	A user from the central DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office, currently known as the DiSSCo CSO.
Researcher	A user who conducts research on natural history collections
Institutional User	A user from a DiSSCo member institution
National Node Coordinator	A user who is the head of a national node

3.5 User Stories

BRID	As a [role]	I want [goal]	So that [reason(s)]	Fit to Statement of Purpose
Accessing Policies				
1	Institutional Policy Lead	to understand the policy requirements of a DiSSCo Service	my institution can join a DiSSCo Service	3
2	DiSSCo CSO user	to share a list of DiSSCo Service policy requirements with DiSSCo members	DiSSCo members can see the requirements they need to meet	3
34	Institutional Policy Lead	to see a list of all DiSSCo policy requirements	I can check whether my policies need to be updated	3
36	Institutional Policy Lead	to be able to find help and guidance on DiSSCo policy requirements	I know how to update my policies so my institution can join a DiSSCo service	3
31	DiSSCo CSO user	to be able to link to relevant DiSSCo and institutional policies when setting up a funding call	researchers can check they can access and sample the required specimens as part of their grant proposal	2
13	Researcher	to be able to access an institution's policies when responding to a funding call	I know I can undertake the planned research before I submit the proposal	2
32	Institutional Policy Lead	a place to store our institution's policies	researchers can access them more easily and we can share the policies with funders	2
42	Institutional Policy Lead	to access relevant policies of other institutions	I can review them when updating my own policy	2
Self-Assessment & Institutional Summary				
3	Institutional	to self-assess our policies	I can see where we meet the	3

	Policy Lead	against DiSSCo requirements	requirements, identify gaps and discover inconsistencies	
33	Institutional Policy Lead	to only have to complete the full self-assessment once	I can save time when reviewing responses in future years or answering new questions	3
41	Institutional Policy Lead	to be able to work on the self-assessment with my institutional colleagues	we can use our combined expertise to complete it	2
37	Institutional Policy Lead	to see what proportion of institutions have policies in each area	I can use this information to help me develop our own policy	2
40	Institutional Policy Lead	to be able demonstrate where our internal policy is due to governmental/ external accreditation requirements	DiSSCo CSO are kept informed of areas where we cannot change our policy	2
DiSSCo CSO - Dashboard				
4	DiSSCo CSO user	to evaluate the overall alignment status of DiSSCo member policies with DiSSCo services policies	I can identify most urgent areas of need for the DiSSCo community to advise on alignment strategies and help develop capacity	3
30	DiSSCo CSO user	to understand where DiSSCo member policies differ from DiSSCo Service policies	I can identify areas of DiSSCo policies requiring supplementation or modification	3
28	DiSSCo CSO user	add a new DiSSCo service or policy to the self-assessment tool and DiSSCo Dashboard	DiSSCo member can assess themselves against the new policy requirements	3
35	DiSSCo CSO user	to send reminders to institutional users to complete or update their self-assessment	I have current information from as many institutions as possible	3

39	DiSSCo CSO user	DiSSCo CSO user I want to be able to change the policy requirement for a DiSSCo service	I can keep the tool up to date if requirements change	3
45	National Node Coordinator	to be able to evaluate the overall alignment status of my National Node institutions with DiSSCo services policies	I can help develop capacity within the national node	2
38	DiSSCo CSO user	to be able to vary policy requirements between DiSSCo services	institutional users can accurately assess their compliance against each DiSSCo service	2

4 Requirements

The requirements for the Policy Tool have been categorised under four components: the DiSSCo Policy Portal, Self-Assessment Tool, Institutional Summary and DiSSCo CSO Dashboard. Each component is described in more detail underneath each heading.

The functional requirements for the Policy Tool have been written in the form of acceptance criteria. Each acceptance criteria is associated with a user story, and these criteria must be met in order for the product to be accepted by the user. This document lists the acceptance criteria and user stories in separate sections, but they can be viewed together in [this spreadsheet](#).

Acceptance criteria have been prioritised using the MoSCoW method. Each criterion has a priority rating assigned to it, with a '4' indicating the product 'must have' the functionality described, a '3' that it 'should have', and a '2' that it 'could have'. Acceptance criteria assigned priority 1, 'won't have', have not been included in this document.

4.1 DiSSCo Policy Portal

4.1.1 Description

The DiSSCo policy portal will be an open repository for DiSSCo policies, as well as a place users can visit to find policy related help, guidance and resources. It could also allow institutions to maintain their own repository of institutional policies which, at their discretion, can be made openly available to others.

4.1.2 Acceptance Criteria

BR ID	AC ID		Priority*
1	1.1	DiSSCo CSO User can upload, edit, remove and replace a DiSSCo Policy	4
	1.2	User can search for a DiSSCo Policy	4
	1.3	User can view and download a DiSSCo Policy	4
	1.4	User can link to a DiSSCo Policy	4
34	34.1	Users can view all DiSSCo policy requirements in one place	4
2	2.1	Users can view the policy requirements for a specific DiSSCo service	4
36	36.4	DiSSCo CSO User can add, upload, edit, remove and replace help and guidance	4
	36.5	Users can access help, guidance, best practice and protocols	4
	36.1	DiSSCo policies can link to further help and guidance	4
31	31.1	DiSSCo CSO Users can create a bespoke list of DiSSCo policies and can link to them	2
32	32.1	Institutional users can upload, replace and delete institutional policies	2
	32.2	Institutional users can set whether their policies are visible to the to the DiSSCo CSO only, to other institutional users or to the general public	2
	32.3	Users can access institutional policies which they have the appropriate access permissions to view.	2
	32.4	Institutional users can set how often they want a reminder to check that an uploaded policy is up to date	2
	32.5	Institutional users can optionally add a contact email address which will be visible to other users	2

13	13.1	Users can access institutional policies relevant to a DiSSCo service call for applications	2
	13.2	Users can view a contact e-mail address for institutional policies which are not shareable	2

*4 = 'Must Have', 3 = 'Should Have', 2 = 'Could Have', 1 = 'Won't Have'

4.2 Self-Assessment Tool

4.2.1 Description

The self-assessment tool will allow institutional users to apply the metadata schema and classification terms to their institutional policies.

4.2.2 Acceptance Criteria

BR ID	AC ID		Priority*
3	3.1	Institutional user can register for and login to an account	4
	3.2	Institutional user can complete the self-assessment	4
	3.3	Institutional user can save progress and come back to the self-assessment at a later time	4
	3.4	Institutional user can request for their self-assessment responses to be removed from the system	4
	3.5	DiSSCo CSO user can remove an institution's self-assessment responses from the system	4
28	28.1	Policy self-assessment tool allows for updates to the metadata schema	4
	28.2	An update to the metadata schema will not result in loss of previously entered data	4
33	33.1	Self-Assessment tool prepopulates with previously submitted responses	4
41	41.1	Institutional users can work collaboratively on the self-assessment	4
36	36.2	Self-Assessment tool can link to help and guidance	3
40	40.1	Self-Assessment tool allows users to enter where a policy requirement	2

		is determined by governmental/external accreditation requirements	
	40.2	Self-Assessment tool allows institutional users to optionally upload and/or link to their institutional policies	2
	40.3	Self-Assessment tool allows users to add comments which will be visible to DiSSCo CSO users	2

*4 = 'Must Have', 3 = 'Should Have', 2 = 'Could Have', 1 = 'Won't Have'

4.3 Institutional Summary

4.3.1 Description

Institutional users will receive an institutional summary once they have completed the self-assessment. The institutional summary will show compliance compared to DiSSCo Policy and will provide links to relevant help and guidance.

4.3.2 Acceptance Criteria

BR ID	AC ID		Priority*
	3.4	Institutional user receives results summary once self-assessment questionnaire is complete	4
3	3.5	Results summary shows where the institution is compliant with DiSSCo policy requirements, and areas where they are not compliant	4
	3.6	Results summary can show a scoring system to rate institutional compliance against DiSSCo policy requirements	3
	3.7	Results summary allows institutional users to filter by policy category	4
36	36.3	Institutional summary can direct institutional users to appropriate help and guidance	4
28	28.4	New information can be added to the institutional summary when the metadata schema updates	4
	37.1	Institutional users can view the proportion of institutions which have adopted each policy requirement	2

37	37.2	Institutional users can opt out of allowing their self-assessment responses to be included in the proportions shown as part of AC37.1	2
42	42.1	Institutional users can access institutional policies set as visible to other institutional users (AC32.2)	2

*4 = 'Must Have', 3 = 'Should Have', 2 = 'Could Have', 1 = 'Won't Have'

4.4 DiSSCo CSO Dashboard

4.4.1 Description

The DiSSCo CSO Dashboard will show the overall state of policy compliance and policy gaps across all DiSSCo members. It will help the DiSSCo CSO identify areas where capacity building and further alignment may be beneficial.

4.4.2 Acceptance Criteria

BR ID	AC ID		Priority*
4	4.1	DiSSCo CSO users can register and login to the DiSSCo Dashboard	4
	4.2	DiSSCo CSO Dashboard can show an individual institution's responses to the self-assessment	4
	4.3	DiSSCo CSO can show the proportion of DiSSCo members compliant or not with a policy requirement	4
	4.4	DiSSCo CSO Dashboard allows selection of multiple policy requirements, showing the proportion of institutions compliant with these policies	4
	4.5	DiSSCo CSO Dashboard allows DiSSCo CSO users to filter by DiSSCo service, which then only shows the policy requirements relevant to that service	3
30	30.2	DiSSCo CSO can view the institutional policies uploaded by DiSSCo Partners	4
	35.1	DiSSCo CSO can set a deadline for the self-assessment to be completed or updated, with reminders automatically sent to institutional users	4

35	35.2	DiSSCo CSO users can select to send reminders only to institutional users who have not completed or updated the self-assessment tool since a selected date	4
	35.3	System records the self-assessment tool date of submission	4
28	28.3	New views can be added to the DiSSCo dashboard when the metadata schema updates	4
	28.5	DiSSCo CSO can inform institutional users about a policy requirement update	4
45	45.1	National node user can register and login to an account	3
	45.2	DiSSCo CSO User can specify which self-assessment data each national node user has permission to access	3
	45.2	National node user can use the functionality listed in AC 4.2-4.5 for the institutions they have access permissions to view	3

*4 = 'Must Have', 3 = 'Should Have', 2 = 'Could Have', 1 = 'Won't Have'

5 Non-Functional Requirements

Category	Requirement
Accessibility	The system should follow the W3C Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.0 (https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG20/).
Availability	The system should be always available during the hours when it is most used. Any maintenance where the system needs to be taken offline should be done outside these times.
	The geographic location of the server should not impede the availability of the system. This means a location with a good quality connection and with minimal network restriction should be chosen.
Backup and recovery	The system should allow for taking backups of data, such that it may be restored to a working state.
	The system should backup data very frequently/seamlessly to avoid any data loss.
	The system should backup in a short period of time (e.g. one minute) with

	minimal disruption.
	In the event of a disaster, the latest backup should be immediately restored, such that the system is offline for less than one hour.
Capacity and scalability	The system must store data effectively and must anticipate the time remaining until all available storage is filled up.
	As the system gets used more often, by more people, the storage available will need to increase.
	The system should be able to scale to the requirements of the full DiSSCo user base without degradation in performance.
Data integrity and validation	System datastores, user interfaces and APIs should be UTF-8 compliant.
	The data store should be able to apply appropriate constraints to maintain the integrity of the data according to the defined data model.
	The data store and interfaces should be able to validate data to ensure compliance with the data model definitions.
Documentation	The system should be accompanied by comprehensive user, installation and administration guides.
	The system should use open source components, and any code generated should be made publicly available under an agreed open source license.
Flexibility and extensibility	The system architecture should be extensible and modular, so that extensions to the original scope can be easily incorporated.
	The system should support ongoing modifications and additions to the data schema and user interfaces without compromising the integrity of the core architecture. As much as possible, this should be possible through system configuration rather than code customisation.
Interoperability	The system should include a RESTful API with CRUD capabilities and appropriate security and authentication. Ideally the same API should be available for external integrations as the system uses for its own user interfaces.
	The system should be able to present and handle data in formats that are compatible with other DiSSCo services and core architectural components.
Localization	The system should provide support the potential for managing the languages of DiSSCo member countries, although the initial interface will be developed in English.
	The system should support regional data formats (e.g. dates and currencies).

Maintainability	Accepted standards and design patterns should be used in the construction of the base architecture.
	The code should be built modularly, such that independent parts accomplish independent tasks. Common coding styles should be used.
Performance	Over reasonably common internet connection speeds, the server should respond to client requests in less than one second.
	Interactions with the server which require processing, such as login and requesting thumbnails of images, should take less than three seconds.
	Querying the database should take less than one second.
Mobility and compatibility	The system should be installable on operating systems that are appropriate for the production environment of a DiSSCo service.
	The system should be compatible with all major browsers (Chrome, Firefox, Edge and Safari).
	During the development process the implications of providing compatibility with major mobile browsers will be explored, as well as the need to scale appropriately for mobile device screen sizes and resolutions.
	The system should be installable on physical or virtual hardware that are appropriate for the production environment of a DiSSCo service.
Regulatory	The system should restrict visibility of sensitive and personally identifiable information to appropriate authenticated users.
Reliability	The system should meet or exceed 99.99% uptime.
Security and privacy	Users must be logged on to add, edit or delete data and files.
	The system should employ user- and role-based access control.
	Users must be accredited members of an institution to edit the data and files for that institution.
	Passwords must not be stored within the system or revealed to users.
	The system should make use of encryption to ensure that data is stored securely. For example, passwords should be stored as SHA1 hashes. Connections should be encrypted to prevent unauthorised listening of communication.
Support	End user and administrative support should be available to users during normal European hours of working.
Usability and	Users should be able to learn to use the system without requiring assistance or

visual design	dedicated training.
	The system should look visually engaging, be attractive to users, and use a consistent design throughout, to encourage use and inspire the confidence of users.
	Tools, information, documents and functionality should be easy to find without reference to guidance.
	Users should be able to navigate the system, workflows and functions with a minimised number of clicks and other interface interactions.
	The system should be easy to remember, so that the casual user is able to return to the system after some period of not having used it, without having to learn everything all over again.
	95% of users should rate the system as enjoyable to use.
	The system should use validation and workflows to minimise the ability of users to make errors.

6 Project Dependencies

6.1 SYNTHESYS+ NA2.1: Harmonisation of Policies and Best Standards

A DiSSCo policy metadata schema is under development as part of the SYNTHESYS+ Network Access (NA) 2.1 task. This metadata schema will form the backbone of the Policy Tool. NA2.1 will produce a metadata schema for the ELViS DiSSCo service, although the design of the schema will be modular and allow for the later addition of other DiSSCo services. The deliverable from this work package is due in October 2022.

6.2 DiSSCo Prepare Task 5.1: Knowledgebase

The DiSSCo Knowledgebase is an open source repository and is currently under development as part of DPP Task 5.1. The Knowledgebase will be the hub for DiSSCo-linked research outputs, guidelines and best practices. All 'must have' acceptance criteria listed under the DiSSCo Policy Portal component can be implemented in the Knowledgebase, and there will be close collaboration with the Knowledgebase team in the development of the full DiSSCo Policy Tool.

6.3 DiSSCo Prepare Task 3.1: Digital maturity tool

The Policy tool needs to support the potential to accommodate related use cases involving the compilation/self-assessment of data from DiSSCo members and the aggregation and summary of this information to support the functions of the DiSSCo CSO. The most notable example of this is the

Digital Maturity Indicator Tool, being developed within Task 3.1 of the DiSSCo Prepare project. This will support the self-assessment of institutions in their efforts to measure various dimensions of their preparedness to engage with DiSSCo services. Other related use cases are emerging across DiSSCo that have similar properties to the Policy tool. While development activities in Task 7.3 will focus on the Policy Tool, the modularity of the tools design, coupled with agile development processes, should enable related self-assessment services to be integrated in the future, should resources allow.

7 General Issues and Challenges

The user interviews raised a number of issues and challenges which will need to be addressed in the next phase of the project:

- DiSSCo members will need to be incentivised to complete the self-assessment activity, and it is therefore important the Policy Tool adds value to an institution's policy management process. Where possible, the help and resources provided should support an institution on how to implement DiSSCo policy within their unique setting, rather than taking an inflexible approach. This will help to ensure the self-assessment process will not be seen as a 'tick box exercise'.
- The Self-Assessment Tool should provide guidance on what would be considered supporting evidence for a policy requirement, as this will help to support the institution in assessing themselves against the alignment criteria. It may also be helpful to distinguish between policy that has been implemented, and policy that has been developed but not yet applied.
- DiSSCo members are often willing to comply with a DiSSCo policy for a particular service (e.g. ELViS), even in instances where the institutional policy differs from DiSSCo requirements. Further work is required to consider how this flexibility might be represented in the self-assessment, as there is some tension between user stories related to assessing institutional compliance with DiSSCo Policy and those that want to understand policy maturity levels within institutions.
- The Policy Tool should be extensible and modular, to allow potential scalability to support business needs which fit the same basic principles. For example, the DiSSCo Digital Maturity Self-Assessment Tool, which will be developed as part of DPP Task 3.1, could be built on the same technical platform, and it could be used for any further development of the SYNTHESYS Collections Self-Assessment Tool (CSAT).
- There is a possibility that a DiSSCo service may specify different policy requirements within a policy component compared to another service. Consideration is required on how policy alignment would be represented in these cases for the Institutional Summary and DiSSCo CSO Dashboard, particularly for the 'top-level' views.

8 Conclusion

This design blueprint outlines the functional and non-functional requirements for the DiSSCo Policy Tool, as well as the synergies with related activities. The next stage of DPP Task 7.3 will focus on the development of the Policy Tool, working closely with the SYNTHESYS+ NA2.1 and DPP Task 5.1 Knowledgebase project teams. Usability testing will be conducted throughout the development process, which will help to ensure that all elements are easy to use and that visualisations in the Institutional Summary and DiSSCo CSO Dashboard are informative. In so far as is possible, the policy tool will also support related usecases such as DiSSCo Prepare Task 3.1.

9 Author Contributions

Authors

Writing – original draft: Lisa French, Matt Woodburn and Vincent Smith.

Writing – review & editing: Jonathan Blettery, Ana Casino, Lisa French, Quentin Groom, Marko Hyvarinen, Tina Loo, Carole Paleco, Julia Pim Reis, Serge Scory, Patrick Semal, Vincent Smith, Laura Tilley, Matt Woodburn.

Conceptualisation and Methodology: Vincent Smith, Ana Casino, Carole Paleco, Quentin Groom, Matt Woodburn, Lisa French.

Investigation, data curation and formal analysis: Lisa French and Matt Woodburn.

Additional contributors

Funding acquisition: Vincent Smith (for this Task)

Project administration: Eva Alonso

Validation: Helen Hardy and Rui Figueira.

Contribution types are drawn from CRediT - [Contributor Roles Taxonomy](#).